

Caring Behaviour of Nurses as A Correlate to Client Care Satisfaction Among Older- Adult Admitted in The Two Tertiary Hospitals in Osun State, Nigeria

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Abstract:

This study investigated caring behaviour of nurses as a correlate to client care satisfaction among older adults admitted in the two tertiary hospitals in Osun State, Nigeria. Descriptive research design of the correlational type was adopted in this study. The sample size consisted of 177 older adults from age 60 years and above admitted into two tertiary hospitals were selected for this study using proportionate distribution and purposive sampling techniques. A self-developed, structured questionnaire was used to elicit information from the respondents. The research instrument was validated and reliability index of 0.79 for Caring behaviour of Nurses and 0.89 for satisfaction with nursing care among older adults were gotten. The data collected through the instrument were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. All hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study revealed that physical caring behaviour ($r = .615$, $p = .000$), psychological caring behaviour,

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social caring behaviour ($r = .628, p = .000$), and spiritual caring ($r = .628, p = .000$) positively related to patients care satisfaction. It was recommended among others that the hospital authorities should recruit more nurses that could take direct care of patients. Also, Government hospitals should implement the regular evaluation of consumer satisfaction in each visit to serve as evidence base for improved quality healthcare services.

Keywords: Caring Behaviour, Nurses, Care Satisfaction, Older Adult,

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Introduction:

Older Adults are distinctive set of people in terms of their physical and mental health. As they increase in age, they often experience one or more chronic condition as a result of their ageing process thus increasing their demand for medical, nursing, and social services. About 92% of older adults have at least one chronic disease while 77% have at least two (National Council on Ageing, 2019). This age related problem, hospitalization and illness create their dependency on nurses for basic needs when on hospital admission. Evidence abound within the health system that is suggestive that older adults' health can improve or that they can cope better with illness when he or she is valued and treated with respect by nurses. However, according to Bucco (2015), older adults' dignity, respect and value are given little attention by nurses and this, often scares them away from the hospital to see alternative care outside hospital which have dangerous health complication on their quality of life.

Caring is an essential human need, a fundamental component of nursing and a unifying focus for the practice of nursing. It involves interpersonal interaction and relationship, a mutually beneficial experience, for both the patient and the nurse. As much as caring is a general need for all ages its significance among older adults cannot be over emphasized. Caring Behaviours are actions of nurses that are concerned with the total wellbeing of patients (Nazloo, Feizi & Salimi, 2019). It involves how nurses should effectively implement their practice in contributing significantly to patient's health and illness. It is central in the quality of care being given to the patient and the developing of a trusting and closer relationship between the patient and the nurse. Caring behaviours improve the quality of care and thus, cause a sense of security, reduction of anxiety, and consensus between caregiver and care recipient (Bergdahl, Ternstedt, Bertero & Andershed, 2019) which subsequently enhance patient satisfaction (Janet & Bronya, 2019).

The ability to provide patients with adequate information, explain, listen and empathize to help them make informed decisions which can have a profound effect on their patient satisfaction is impaired due to ineffective communication between nurses and patients. This leads to misinterpretation by older adults, with dissatisfied patients more likely to change healthcare facility they applied for treatment and care (Kol, Arikan, Ilaslan, Akinci, Kocak-Collegian, 2018). More so, Brennan, Knee, Leahy, Michael, & Heidi-Ann, (2019) stated that some nurses communicate with older adults impolitely, speaking too loudly concerning their private matters, not giving them enough time to tell their stories, failing to listen to them and not involving them in their own care as a result of the workload and stress they encounter in their daily practice. Older Adults are not satisfied with nurse caring behaviours because nurses did not seem to understand how to care for them with their inherent frailties (Brennan, Knee, Leahy, Michael, & Heidi-Ann, 2019). They are not satisfied with their care because nurses do not act in the way that the older adults can participate and make decision according to their own values from an informed position.

Patient/Client satisfaction is an expression of patient's over all judgement on the quality of care being given (Rutter, Savona, Glonti, Bibby, Cummins & Finegood, 2017), which could be determined by interaction of health care provider with the patients, emotional tone

of care given, healing and cure that follow and the patient's judgment of improved health outcomes (Singh, & Prasher, 2019). According to Nazloo, Feizi & Salimi (2019) patient/client satisfaction is an important indicator of quality health care and influences patient compliance and continuity of care. Achieving client care satisfaction is a main factor to achieving desirable result in the healthcare system, however, nursing care is one of the major components of healthcare system (Karaca, & Durna, 2019) that involves the provision of a caring relationship which facilitates health and healing process. It provides physical, psychological, social and spiritual care (Karaca, & Durna, 2019) through nurse caring behaviour, which is a determinant of quality health care with the ultimate goal of care satisfaction.

However, the researcher also discovered that many older adults prefer to be treated at home than to be taken down to hospital for their care as they do not experience the ultimate care they desired. The researcher decided to assess the correlation between caring behaviour of nurses among older adults and client care satisfaction. This is needed to be maximally explored so that strategies could be implemented to improve the quality of care and address problems experienced by older adults.

This study investigated caring behaviour of nurses as a correlate to client care satisfaction among older adults admitted in the two tertiary hospitals in Osun State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study examined:

- i. the level of satisfaction of older adults with caring behaviour of nurses;
- ii. the caring behaviour of nurses expected by older adults;
- iii. the relationship between nurse physical caring behaviour and client care satisfaction;
- iv. the relationship between nurse social caring behaviour and client care satisfaction;
- v. the relationship between nurse psychological caring behaviour and client care satisfaction; and
- vi. the relationship between nurse spiritual caring behaviour and client care satisfaction.

Research Questions

The research questions raised in this study are:

1. What is the level of satisfaction of older adults with caring behaviour of nurses?
2. What are the caring behaviour of nurses expected by older adults?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were generated:

1. There is no significant relationship between nurse physical caring behaviour and client care satisfaction
2. There is no significant relationship between nurse social caring behaviour and client care satisfaction
3. There is no significant relationship between nurse psychological caring behaviour and client care satisfaction
4. There is no significant relationship between nurse spiritual caring behaviour and client care satisfaction.

Methodology

This study utilized descriptive research design of the correlational type to establish a correlation caring behavior of nurses and client care satisfaction among admitted older adults in the two tertiary hospitals in Osun State. The population for this study were 282 older adults from age 60 years and above admitted into Male and Female wards of Surgical, Medical and Orthopedic of Obafemi Awolowo Teaching Hospital and Ladoke Akintola University of Technology Teaching Hospital both in Osun State, Nigeria. A total of were 177 older adults from age 60 years and above admitted were selected for this study using proportionate distribution and purposive sampling techniques.

A self-developed, structured questionnaire was used to elicit information from the respondents. The questionnaire was developed using study objectives and research questions in line with literature reviewed. The questionnaire was divided into three sections. The questionnaire consists of three sections: a) Socio demographic profile (b) Caring behavior of nurses (c) Assessment on client care satisfaction. Section A consisted of information about Socio-Demographic profile of the Respondents such as Age, Gender, name of ward admitted into and number of days on admission. Section B had 4 subscale physical, psychological, social and spiritual caring behaviours. It has 20 questions to be measured on 4 point Likert scale with 4 denoting strongly agree to 1 denoting strongly disagree. Section C consisted of 4 subscale caring, patient-centred care, communication and Responsiveness. It consisted of 23 questions to be measured on 4 point Likert scale with 4 denoting completely satisfied to 1 denoting not satisfied.

The face and content validity of the instrument was validated by experts in the field of Nursing Science and Tests & Measurement. Necessary corrections were made by the expert and they ascertained that the instrument could elicit adequate information to achieve the stated objectives. Reliability of the instrument was tested using Cronbach's Alpha model technique to ensure internal consistency of the instrument. The data collected were analysed and Cronbach's alpha values of 0.79 for Caring behaviour of Nurses and 0.89 for satisfaction with nursing care among older adults were gotten.

The data collected through the instrument were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The research questions were answered using frequency counts, means, standard deviation and percentages. Hypotheses 1 – 4 were tested using inferential statistics of Pearson Product Moment Correlation. All hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the level of satisfaction of older adults with caring behaviour of nurses?

Table 1: Descriptive analysis on level of satisfaction of older adults with caring behaviour of nurses

Criteria	Category	Frequency	%	Mean	Remark
Completely Satisfied	70-92	-	-	48.74 (53%)	Number of the respondents who are completely satisfied with caring behaviour of nurses
Averagely Satisfied	47-69	117	66.1		Number of the respondents who are averagely satisfied with caring behaviour of nurses
Barely Satisfied	24-46	39	22.0		Number of the respondents who are barely satisfied with caring behaviour of nurses
Not Satisfied	1-23	21	11.9		Number of the respondents who are not satisfied with caring behaviour of nurses

Table 1 above presents the level of satisfaction of older adults with caring behaviour of nurses into four (4) different domains. The domains were categorized as Not Satisfied (1-23), Barely Satisfied (24-46), Averagely Satisfied (47-69), and Completely Satisfied (70-92). Majority 117 (66.1%) of the respondents were averagely satisfied with caring behaviour of nurses, 39 (22%) respondents were barely satisfied with caring behaviour of nurses, and the remaining 21 (11.9%) were not satisfied with caring behaviour of nurses. The mean score is 48.74 (53%). The implication of this results is that the level of satisfaction of older adults with caring behaviour of nurses is moderate. Figure i further revealed the level of satisfaction of older adults with caring behaviour of nurses at a glance

Figure i: Bar Chart showing the level of satisfaction of older adults with caring behaviour of nurses

Research Question 2: What are the caring behaviour of nurses expected by older adults?

Table 2: Descriptive analysis on the caring behavior of nurses expected by older adults

Nurses' caring Behaviour	Mean (%)	Std. Dev	Rank
Physical	11.05 (55.3)	3.64	2 nd
Psychological	10.68 (53.4)	3.62	3 rd
Social	10.95 (54.8)	3.98	1 st
Spiritual	10.95 (54.8)	3.50	4 th
Overall mean score of Nurses' caring behaviour = 43.63 (54.6%)			

Table 2 reveals the caring behaviour of nurses expected by older adults to be physical caring behaviour, psychological caring behaviour, social caring behaviour, and spiritual caring behaviour. Among these caring behaviours, physical caring behaviour was found to be 55.3% rated by the patients, social and spiritual were rated 54.8% respectively and psychological

caring behaviour was rated 53.4%. It could therefore be said that all the components of nurses caring behaviour were moderately rated. Figure ii further revealed the caring behaviour of nurses expected by older adults at a glance

Figure ii: Bar Chart showing caring behaviour of nurses expected by older adults

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between nurse physical caring behaviour and client care satisfaction

Table 3: Pearson Product Moment correlation showing the relationship between physical caring behaviour of nurses and care satisfaction by older adults

		Clients care satisfaction	Physical Caring behaviour
Clients care satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	1	.615**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	177	177
Physical Caring behaviour	Pearson Correlation	.615**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	177	177

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 3 showed that the r-cal value of 0.615 is significant at 0.05 level of significance. This revealed a significant relationship between physical caring behaviour of nurses and care satisfaction by older adults ($r = .615, p = .000$). The null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there was significant relationship between nurse physical caring behaviour and client care satisfaction. The result shows that the physical caring behaviour of nurses is positively and moderately related to patients care satisfaction. The implication of this is that physical caring behaviour of nurses has good relationship with patients care satisfaction.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between nurse social caring behaviour and client care satisfaction.

Table 4: Pearson Product Moment correlation showing the relationship between Social caring behaviour of nurses and care satisfaction by older adults

		Clients care satisfaction	Social Caring behaviour
Clients care satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	1	.628**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	177	177
Social Caring behaviour	Pearson Correlation	.628**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	177	177

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4 showed that the r-cal value of 0.628 is significant at 0.05 level of significance. This revealed a significant relationship between social caring behaviour of nurses and care satisfaction by older adults ($r = .628, p = .000$). The null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there was significant relationship between nurse social caring behaviour and client care satisfaction. The result shows that the social caring behaviour of nurses is positively and moderately related to patients care satisfaction. The implication of this is that social caring behaviour of nurses has good relationship with patients care satisfaction.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between nurse psychological caring behaviour and client are satisfaction.

Table 5: Pearson Product Moment correlation showing the relationship between Psychological caring behaviour of nurses and care satisfaction by older adults

		Clients care satisfaction	Psychological Caring behaviour
Clients care satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	1	.695**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	177	177
Psychological Caring behaviour	Pearson Correlation	.695**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	177	177

****.** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 5 showed that the r-cal value of 0.695 is significant at 0.05 level of significance. This revealed a significant relationship between psychological caring behaviour of nurses and care satisfaction by older adults ($r = .695, p = .000$). The null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there was significant relationship between nurse psychological caring behaviour and client care satisfaction. The result shows that the psychological caring behaviour of nurses is positively and highly related to patients care satisfaction. The implication of this is that psychological caring behaviour of nurses has good relationship with patients care satisfaction.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant relationship between nurse spiritual caring behaviour and client care satisfaction.

Table 6: Pearson Product Moment correlation showing the relationship between Spiritual caring behaviour of nurses and care satisfaction by older adults

		Clients care satisfaction	Spiritual Caring behaviour
Clients care satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	1	.671**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	177	177
Spiritual Caring behaviour	Pearson Correlation	.671**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	177	177

****.** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 6 showed that the r-cal value of 0.671 is significant at 0.05 level of significance. This revealed a significant relationship between spiritual caring behaviour of nurses and care

satisfaction by older adults ($r = .671, p = .000$). The null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there was significant relationship between nurse spiritual caring behaviour and client care satisfaction. The result shows that the spiritual caring behaviour of nurses is positively and highly related to patients care satisfaction. The implication of this is that spiritual caring behaviour of nurses has good relationship with patients care satisfaction.

Discussion

The finding of study revealed that the level of satisfaction of older adults with caring behaviour of nurses showed that majority of the clients were averagely satisfied with caring behaviour of nurses. The implication of this result is that the level of satisfaction of older adults with caring behaviour of nurses is moderate. This study corroborates the previous findings of Kol et al. (2018) and Kokeb et al. (2015) that the adult patients were found to be satisfied with the nursing care they have received.

It was also revealed that the caring behaviour of nurses expected by older adult patients were physical caring behaviour, psychological caring behaviour, social caring behaviour, and spiritual caring behaviour. Among these caring behaviours, physical caring behaviour was found to be the highest. This finding is in line with the findings of Zabolypour, Dastan, Ghorbani, Anbari and Mohammadi (2016) who concluded that caring behaviours ranked as most important by patients is the physical caring.

Finding from the result shows that the physical caring behaviour of nurses is positively related to patients care satisfaction. The implication of this is that physical caring behaviour of nurses has good relationship with patients care satisfaction. This physical care captures the very essence of how nurses effectively implement their practice thereby contributing significantly to patient's health and illness. When nurses provide good nursing care to the patients, it has a positive impact on patients' life and also on his satisfaction (Öztunç, 2015). Caring behaviours can enhance the quality of care provided thereby creating a sense of belonging, allowing the patient to accept care and promote nurse-patient relationship, ultimately enhancing patient satisfaction (Batbaatar, Dorjdagva, Luvsannyam, Mario, Savino & Amenta, 2016).

It was also revealed that there was significant relationship between nurse social caring behaviour and client care satisfaction. The result shows that the social caring behaviour of nurses is positively related to patients care satisfaction. The implication of this is that social caring behaviour of nurses has good relationship with patients care satisfaction. This is in line with the submission of Bucco (2015) who found relationship between nurse social caring behaviour and client care satisfaction. The social satisfaction with care is important factor in improving the quality of life of older adults' patients.

It was also revealed from the result that there was significant relationship between nurse psychological caring behaviour and client care satisfaction. The result shows that the psychological caring behaviour of nurses is positively related to patients care satisfaction. The implication of this is that psychological caring behaviour of nurses has good relationship with

patients care satisfaction. This finding supported the work of Flynn (2016) who reported that the psychological caring behaviour is the most important behaviour in determining client care satisfaction. With demonstration of psychological caring behaviour, the quality of care increases the sense of security in patients and reduces patient's anxiety (Bergdahl, Ternestedt, Bertero & Andershed, 2019).

The last findings showed that there was significant relationship between nurse spiritual caring behaviour and client care satisfaction. The result shows that the spiritual caring behavior of nurses is positively related to patients care satisfaction. The implication of this is that spiritual caring behavior of nurses has good relationship with patients care satisfaction. This finding is in consonance with the study of Bucco (2015) who concluded that spiritual caring behavior of nurses is positively related to patients care satisfaction.

Conclusion

Sequel to the findings of this study, it was concluded that majority of the patients were moderately satisfied with the nurses' care behaviour. It was also concluded that patient satisfaction was relevant to the nurses' caring behaviours. Therefore, creating a caring environment and improving the nurses' caring behaviours may improve the patient quality of life and that will finally improve the patients' satisfaction. In addition, nurse physical, social, psychological and spiritual caring behaviour were related to client care satisfaction. This study therefore concluded that nurses' care behaviour is a strong predictor of patients' satisfaction.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made.

- 1) The hospital authorities should recruit more nurses that could take direct care of patients
- 2) Government hospitals should implement the regular evaluation of consumer satisfaction in each visit to serve as evidence base for improved quality healthcare services.
- 3) Nurses should be trained in patient-centered caring skills and that training is extended to the entire organization. Individualized care builds trust in care.
- 4) Nurses are recommended to improve their own behaviours in all aspects of the caring behaviours.

References

- Batbaatar, E., Dorjdagva, J., Luvsannyam, A., Mario- Savino, M., & Amenta, P. (2017). Determinants of Patient Satisfaction: A systematic review. Perspective in *Public Health Sage Journals*. <https://doi.org/19.1177/175>.
- Bergdahl, E., Ternstedt, B., & Andershed, B. (2019). The theory of a co- creative process in advanced palliative home care nursing encounters: A qualitative approach over time. *International Journal for Human Caring* 4 (21) 208 – 213.
- Brennan, M, J., Knee, A, B., Leahy, E, J., Michael, J & Heidi-Ann. (2019). An acute care for Elders' quality improvement program for complex, High cost patients yielding savings for the system. *Journal of Hospital Medicine*. 8(2), 34 – 48
- Bucco, T. (2015). The Relationship between Patients' Perception of Nurse Caring Behaviours, Nurses' Perception of Nurse Caring Behaviours and Patient Satisfaction in the Emergency Department. Seton Hall University. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/Scholarship.shu.edu/dissertations> retrieved 5/11/2019.
- Flynn, S (2016). Who cares? A Critical discussion of the value of caring from a patient and healthcare professional perspective. *International journal of orthopaedic and trauma nursing*. <https://doi.org/10.1016>
- Janet, H. Y., Bronya, H. K., (2019). Patient satisfaction: Concept analysis in the healthcare context. *Journal of American Geriatric Society*, 64(6), 1223-1232
- Karaca, A., & Durna, Z. (2019). Patient satisfaction with the quality of nursing care. *Nursing open*, 6(2), 535–545.<https://doi:10.1002/nop2.237>.
- Kokeb, H. E., Akilew, A. A., Fisseha, Z. A., Tesfaye, B. G., & Mulunesh, A. B. (2016). Adult Patients' Satisfaction with Inpatient Nursing Care and Associated Factors in an Ethiopian Referral Hospital, Northeast, Ethiopia. *Advances in Nursing*, 7(2), 56 – 65
- Kol, E., Arikian, F., Ilaslan, E., Akinci, M. A., Kocak-Collegian, M. C. (2018). A quality indicator for the evaluation of nursing care: Determination of patient satisfaction and related factors at a University hospital in the Mediterranean Region. *Aging and mental health Journal* 21 (3), 327-335
- National Council on Aging (2019). Healthy Aging Facts Retrieved online on 22/1/2020.
- Nazloo, S. H., Feizi, A., Salimi, S. (2019). Predictors of nursing care behaviours in critical care units. *The Journal of Urmia Nursing and Midwifery*, 17(5), 371- 378.

- Öztunç, G (2015). Comparison of Nursing Care Perceptions between Patients who had Surgical Operation and Nurses Who Provided Care to those Patients. *International Journal of Caring Sciences* 8(3), 625 – 632.
- Rutter, H., Savona, N., Glonti, K., Bibby, J., Cummins, S., Finegood, D. (2017). The need for a complex systems of model of evidence for public Health. *View point*, 390(1), 57 – 64. <https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6739>.
- Singh, A., A Prasher, A. (2019). Measuring healthcare service quality from patients' perspective: using Fuzzy AHP application. *Total Quality Management & Business*, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14783363.2017.1302794>
- Zabolypour, S., Dastan, K., Ghorbani, S., Anbari, A., Mohammadi, S. (2016). Investigating the Quality of Caring Behaviours of Nurses and Patient Satisfaction in Shahid Beheshti Hospital of Yasuj. *J Res Dev Nurs Midwifery. Spring & Summer*, 13 (1):25-31.

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